

Summary statistics of rDNA polymorphisms in wild and cultivated rice.

Sample	Wild	Cultivated			Total
		Total	Indica	Japonica	
Spacer length variants (no.)	36	15	14	13	42
Phenotypes (no.)	40	48	36	28	80
Diversity	2.99	2.57	2.33	2.38	2.85
Sample size (no.)	83	398	228	170	481

All six slvs occurring in *O. sativa* but not in *O. rufipogon* were rare ($f < 0.01$). In contrast, all of the slvs but one occurring in both *O. rufipogon* and *O. sativa* were observed at much higher frequencies ($f > 0.02$) in *O. sativa*. A majority of the 27 slvs occurring only in *O. rufipogon* were infrequent or rare ($f < 0.02$), but a few of them were detected at sizeable frequencies (0.025-0.095). Overall, no drastic difference existed in the composition of slvs between *O. rufipogon* and *O. sativa*. About equal numbers of slvs were observed in indica and japonica samples. However, distribution of slvs is clearly differentiated between indica and japonica rice groups: indica rice is preferentially associated with longer slvs and japonica rice with shorter ones. Furthermore, indica rice is dominated by one slv, whereas, in japonica rice, two common slvs were observed at about equal frequencies.

The combination of slvs observed in an accession is called a phenotype. Eighty phenotypes, made up of the 42 slvs, were observed in the total sample; the composition of the phenotypes varied from one-banded (containing only one slv) to six-banded, with the one-banded type being the most common. In contrast to the slvs, it is surprising that more phenotypes were observed in *O. sativa* than in *O. rufipogon*. The phenotype occurring most frequently in the *O. rufipogon* group was also observed with highest frequency in *O. sativa*. However, only a few phenotypes were common between *O. rufipogon* and *O. sativa*. More phenotypes were detected in indicas than in japonicas. While all of the phenotypes occurring at frequencies more than 0.01 were observed in both indica and japonica groups, these groups differed substantially in phenotypic composition.

In summary, our analysis established that common wild rice is much more diverse in rDNA slvs than is cultivated rice, but cultivated rice has more slv combinations than does wild rice. This indicates that recombination, functioning to assemble various slvs into individual varieties, has played an important role in the evolution of cultivated rice. This observation might have some implications in resolving a recurring issue concerning the relative amount of genetic variation in wild and cultivated species. It is well recognized that the cultivated forms are usually phenotypically more numerous than their wild relatives, which leads many to believe that cultivated species contain more genetic variation than their wild relatives. The reverse had been argued with the availability of data from molecular marker analyses.

More slvs (presumably with correspondence to alleles) with fewer phenotypes in the wild species compared with fewer slvs with more phenotypes in the cultivated species, as observed in this study, might explain the contrasting patterns in phenotype and DNA diversity of wild and cultivated species. ■

A research program for on-farm conservation of rice genetic resources

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More than 75,000 accessions of cultivated *Oryza sativa* are stored in the International Rice Genebank at IRRI, thus ensuring their security and continued availability for rice improvement. However, from an evolutionary point of view, this ex situ conservation is static: the adaptation of stored varieties to the biotic and abiotic environment is frozen. Thus, in addition to efforts toward genebank efficiency, research is needed on a complementary approach to ex situ conservation.

On-farm conservation is dynamic and aims to promote adapting genetic resources by using the evolutionary processes that

created the diversity of rice varieties. On-farm conservation of crop genetic resources is defined as the continued cultivation and management of a diverse set of crop populations by farmers in the agroecosystems where a crop has evolved.

Despite increasing interest in on-farm conservation, knowledge on the meaning of this approach is still limited. Before implementing on-farm conservation, we need improved knowledge of its driving force: farmers' management of diversity.

Our research program for on-farm conservation started in April 1995 with funding from the Swiss Agency for Development and Cooperation. The objective is to identify opportunities to involve farmers' managed systems in the conservation of rice genetic resources. To accomplish this, we will study the management of rice diversity by farmers and its genetic implications.

We have used two theoretical planning frameworks (Figs. 1 and 2). Our research will address the socioeconomic, socio-cultural, environmental, and genetic aspects of farmers' management of diversity. We will also study farmers' management of diversity and its consequences using several combinations of factors that can influence diversity: market interaction (low/high), ethnic origin of farmers (minority/majority), and environmental heterogeneity (low/high) (Fig. 1).

We will pay particular attention to within-variety genetic polymorphism, which is the basis of evolutionary changes. The findings will lead us to assess other sources of genetic diversity (Fig. 2). The focus will be on the rainfed lowland ecosystem where the co-occurrence of modern and traditional varieties is expected. Study locations will be in India, Philippines, and Vietnam.

1. A conceptual model of factors influencing farmers' management of diversity (from Bellon et al 1995).

2. Factors influencing the genetic polymorphism of a land race (L_1) leading to a second land race (L_2). Farmers may also decide to create a distinct land race (L_3) (from Pham et al 1995).

One of the roles of on-farm conservation research is to test new strategies. These involve farmers managing a sample of genetic diversity in addition to their own varieties. Three ways to complement "classical" on-farm conservation are reintroducing varieties, introducing alien

varieties, and introducing composite populations. We will test the feasibility of these new strategies in developing the necessary links between ex situ and in situ conservation of rice genetic resources (Bellon et al 1995).

Cited references

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Genetics

Genetics of the new plant type

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The genetical architecture of 12 quantitative characters of interest to rice breeders has been investigated in two crosses, Jinmibyeo/Gaok (cross 1) and Sangnam-batbyeo/Kemandi Pance (cross 2), chosen at random from among those made in IRRI's new plant type program. Individuals of the basic generations (P_1 , P_2 , F_1 , F_2 , B_1 and B_2), F_3 , and triple test cross families ($F_2 \times P_1$, $F_2 \times P_2$, and $F_2 \times F_1$) were raised in a single, completely randomized block, one for each cross. Each block also contained plants of IR72 and IR74 as checks.

The parents of these crosses differed significantly for most characters, except for the proportion of filled spikelets and grain yield in cross 1 and 100-grain weight in cross 2. While three characters—panicle number, grain yield, and dry matter—displayed heterosis in the first cross, none did in the second. All of the characters in both crosses were heritable. Their heritabilities ranged from 0.65 for panicle length to 0.04 for harvest index in cross 1, and from 0.77 for dry matter to 0.14 for 100-grain weight in cross 2. The genetical architecture of the characters in cross 1 was of the relatively simple type in which the genes involved displayed either additive effects only or additive and dominance